

**THE ENGLISH WRITING PROFICIENCY AMONG THE GRADE 11 AND 12
STUDENTS OF HOUSE OF ACHIEVERS LEARNING CENTER: BASIS FOR
TEACHING STRATEGY IMPROVEMENT**

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Abstract

Writing is known as an important skill of a student to be developed for this is one of the methods of communication that are mostly used to convey feelings. Further development of writing is an important aspect of organizing thoughts and ideas towards progress of English language proficiency. The study was pursued to establish the English writing proficiency of senior high school students enrolled at the House of Achievers Learning Center. Also, the researcher tends to determine the significant difference of the senior high school students when they are divided into strands. The study was designed to be survey research. The sample used for this study is 185 students and the constructed questionnaire was distributed to these respondents. The researcher used the F-test or ANOVA to determine the significant difference of the strands. The collected data showed that the mean total of the three main aspects: grammar; organization; and mechanics, falls to the category of good and fair. Specifically, the computed mean in grammar is 17.08 (Good), 3.96 (Fair) in organization, and 17.84 (Good) in mechanics. The ANOVA test showed significance in English writing proficiency in the strands.

Keywords: *Writing, Grammar, Organization, Mechanics, Senior High School Students, Strategy Improvement*

INTRODUCTION

In the present system of education, there are five macro skills: Listening, Speaking, Reading, Writing, and Viewing. Among these five macro skills, writing is one of the most important aspects that everyone needs to develop because writing is used by people to communicate their feelings and experiences. It is also considered as a weapon to criticize the work of man. In literature, writing suggests its importance in the sense of preserving important records of knowledge and events of one's culture so that there will be an available account to pass from one generation to the next. Man's memory has its limits, but writing transcends them. It relieves him of the burden of trying to remember everything since he can access the information documented in writing if he needs it. When he has an idea, he may write it down since he knows that if he forgets it later, the writing will always be there to help him remember. ([Buzzi, O. & Grimes, 2012](#)). The objective of setting your working environment is to allow your ideas and words to flow freely, unimpeded by interruptions. This article is another step towards reaching your personal and professional objectives. Consider and respond to the question of why you are obtaining a degree. It might be a mix of causes, such as to demonstrate to your children your dedication to school, to gain a promotion, to pursue a goal you never realized, or to improve your performance in your present position. Regardless of your response, you are in your degree program for a retake. ([Walburg, 2017](#)) One should be knowledgeable enough to successfully produce his ideas and emotions. Someone can effectively write his purpose if he has the knowledge about the language he used. Perhaps, writing is

easy for those native speakers of the English language, while it is difficult for those non-native speakers. But, still, both native and non-native speakers have rules to follow in the process of good writing. Most of these rules are widely available in various books related to English Language. It's important to recognize that communication studies are an interdisciplinary area that borrows from many other disciplines. The fields of philosophy, theology, psychology, anthropology, business, graphic design, and many more may all be represented in a student's study. (Renegar, 2015). Writing gets around the fact that people can't remember everything. It keeps him from having to try to remember everything, which is impossible. If he needs to find a certain fact, he can find it written down somewhere. He can write down ideas as they come to him, knowing that if he forgets them, he can always look back at what he has written to remember them. (Buzzi & Grimes & Alistair, 2012)

This study aims to know how proficient the writing skills of the students in terms of grammar, organization and mechanics. A good skill of writing enables the student to have a good composing process that helps to stimulate and refine their skills with the English language. Upon knowing the level of the proficiency of the students, Senior High School teachers will be able to address the needs of their students with regards to writing. Specifically, it aims to answer the following: What is The English Writing Proficiency of the Senior High School students of Pamantasan ng Cabuyao in terms of: 1.1 Grammar 1.2 Organization 1.3 Mechanics and 2. Is there a significant difference in the English Writing Proficiency of the Seniors High School student of Mary and Jesus School Inc. when they are grouped according to strand?

METHODS

Research Design

This study used the survey research. A survey design provides a quantitative or numeric description of trends, attitudes, or opinions of a population by studying a sample of that population. From sample results, the researcher generalizes or draws inferences to the population.

Respondents of the study

For the gathering of quantitative data, a sample size is determined with the use of Stratified Random Sampling. Stratified Random Sampling is used by the researchers in selecting the respondents included in this study. The

researcher will use the Slovin's formula $n = \frac{N}{1+Ne^2}$ in determining the sample size of the respondents.

There are 343 total populations of Grade 11 students in the House of Achievers Learning Center. The sample is 185 Grade 11 students.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought the approval from the principal, then finally starts the survey. The scores of the survey will be taken and these data will be coded, tallied, and treated using the mean, standard deviation, and Anova of significant difference.

The mean and the standard deviation are used to determine the level of the writing proficiency of the students, while the Anova is employed to determine the significant difference of the different strands.

Instrumentation

The instrument to be used is a researcher made questionnaire. The researchers constructed all parts of the questionnaire. It is composed of three main aspects, namely: grammar, organization, and mechanics. The questionnaire is to be validated through face validation by the English Senior High School teachers of House of Achievers Learning Center.

Data Analysis

This describes the statistical measures utilized in the study after the data were gathered through the instruments or the questionnaires.

Slovin’s Formula- the researcher will use the Slovin’s Formula in determining the sample size of the population.

Formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

- n= sample size
- N= total population
- e= margin of error (0.05)

Arithmetic Mean the researcher will use the arithmetic mean to get the average score of the respondents.

The formula is:

Where:

Σx = summation of scores

N= number of cases

ANOVA (Analysis of Variance)—the researchers used Analysis of Variance or the F-test to determine the significant difference of more than two groups. If there are only two groups being compared, the t-test is usually used but since the researchers compared the English Writing Proficiency of more than two strands, one-way ANOVA is to be used.

Scale- the researcher used the following scale to interpret the computed value.

Grammar (30 items)

Mean’s Scale	Verbal Interpretation
24.80- 30	Excellent
18.60-24.79	Very Good
12.40-18.59	Good
6.20-12.39	Fair
1.0-6.19	Needs Improvement

Organization (10 items)

Mean’s Scale	Verbal Interpretation
8.80-10	Excellent

6.60-8.79	Very Good
4.40-6.59	Good
2.20-4.39	Fair
1.0-2.19	Needs Improvement

Mechanics (30 items)

Mean's Scale	Verbal Interpretation
24.80- 30	Excellent
18.60-24.79	Very Good
12.40-18.59	Good
6.20-12.39	Fair
1.0-6.19	Needs Improvement

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Table 1
The English Writing Proficiency in terms of Grammar

Strand	No. of respondents	Scores	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Accountancy, Business and Management	50	833	16.66	Good
General Academic Track	30	557	18.57	Good
Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics	79	1448	18.33	Good
Technical and Vocational Livelihood – Information and Communication Technology	26	321	12.35	Fair
Total	185	3159	17.08	Good

Table 1 shows that General Academic Track gathered the highest median score of 18.57 with the verbal interpretation of Good, it is followed by the Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics strand with the mean score of 18.33 and a verbal interpretation of Good. Accountancy, Business and Management strand is on the 3rd spot with a mean score of 16.66 with the verbal interpretation of Good. Lastly, the Technical and Vocational Livelihood – Information and Communication Technology got a mean score of 12.35 with a verbal interpretation of Fair.

Data show that majority of the strand in Mary and Jesus School Inc. is Good in Grammar. It is good that students know the basic rules in grammar because it will serve as their foundation in writing proficiently. In the study conducted by [Selwyn & Assemat \(2020\)](#), Because writing requires students to synthesize information, it is widely acknowledged as a powerful educational tool; hence, kids who struggle with writing may also struggle with their overall academic performance.

Undergraduates, according to [Selwyn & Assemat's \(2020\)](#) findings, individuals respect the ability but do not believe they have a significant competency in many soft skills, especially written communication, and this is described as a "knowledge and skill." Students who don't believe in themselves generally avoid challenging assignments, which may be detrimental to their learning and growth.

It is good to note that making the right decisions when speaking or writing in the second language (L2) requires grammatical proficiency. Among the first facets of a language to be studied, grammar is considered essential. Learning the grammar of a language is the first step toward becoming fluent in that language. The capacity to communicate well and be understood by others depends on one's command of grammar. Good writing is also possible with a solid grasp of grammar. ([Sioco & De Vera, 2020](#))

Table 2
The English Writing Proficiency in terms of Organization

Strand	No. of respondents	Scores	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Accountancy, Business and Management	50	182	3.64	Fair
General Academic Track	30	148	4.93	Good
Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics	79	340	4.30	Fair
Technical and Vocational Livelihood – Information and Communication Technology	26	62	2.38	Fair
Total	185	732	3.96	Fair

Based on the data shown above, the result yields to fair in terms of organization in the English Writing Proficiency of the Grade 11 Senior High school Students of House of Achievers Learning Center. General Academic Strand has the highest mean score of 4.93 with the verbal interpretation of Good. On the other hand, Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics strands got 4.30 mean score with a verbal interpretation of Fair, it was followed by Accountancy, Business and Management strand with a mean score of 3.64 with a verbal interpretation of Fair and lastly the Technical and Vocational Livelihood – Information and Communication Technology strand with the 2.38 mean score and Fair verbal interpretation.

Unlike grammar, organization is harder for the respondents to answer since they got a lower median score. [Berkant \(2020\)](#) says effective organization includes correct formatting, logical arrangement, and coherent devices. The

study stated it's a kind of communication engineering beneficial in public speaking and introspection. The evolving style of writing conveys ideas, thoughts, and wishes to readers. For correct communication, this medium must be flawless, with clearly readable and intelligible content, while Filipino pupils are trained to explain their views explicitly in English. Cohesive devices help them make their content more authorial. According to [Berkant \(2020\)](#), Grammatical and textual knowledge are both parts of organizational knowledge. Understanding a text requires determining its coherence and rhetorical design. A text's rhetorical structure is shown by the order of its information. This study refers to coherence in rhetorical arrangement. Cohesion and coherence are essential for conveying meaning to raters, according to the research. Therefore, the researchers evaluated ideational linkages between sentences in addition to the use of cohesive ties.

Table 3
The English Writing Proficiency in terms of Mechanics

Strand	No. of respondents	Scores	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Accountancy, Business and Management	50	610	12.20	Fair
General Academic Track	30	603	20.10	Very Good
Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics	79	1773	22.44	Very Good
Technical and Vocational Livelihood – Information and Communication Technology	26	314	12.08	Fair
Total	185	3300	17.84	Good

Table 3 shows that Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics strand got the highest median score of 22.44 with the verbal interpretation of Very good. It is followed by General Academic Track with the median score of 20.10 and with a Very Good verbal interpretation also. On the other hand, the Accountancy, Business and Management strand and Technical and Vocational Livelihood – Information and Communication Technology strand got a verbal interpretation of Fair with a median score of 12.20 and 12.08 respectively.

Overall, in terms of Mechanics, the Grade 11 Senior High School students of House of Achievers Learning Center got a median score of 17.84 with a verbal interpretation of Good. Research strongly suggests that Teaching grammar encompasses any method of instruction that brings students' attention to a particular grammatical form in a way that facilitates their metalinguistic understanding of the form and/or their processing of the form in comprehension and/or production, allowing them to internalize the form. ([Diaz, et al, 2019](#))

Table 5

The significant difference of English Writing Proficiency of the Respondents according to Strand

Source	SS	Df	MS	F ratio
Factor	5312063.05	4	1328015.763	
Error	6416437.35	10	641643.735	2.07
Total	11728500.4	14		

Using the F distribution, the critical value is $F(4, 10, 0.05) = 3.4780$ or 3.48

Using the Analysis of Variance Technique (ANOVA), the null hypothesis is rejected. It means that the English Writing Proficiency of the Selected Grade 11 Senior High School Students is significant when they are grouped according to strand. Therefore, the approaches and techniques used in teaching writing to Grade 11 Senior High School students must be different because their strength and weaknesses in writing are different. And since writing is a complex and challenging activity for many students, teachers should focus on the grammatical concepts that are essential for the clear communication of meaning. Through detailed studies of students' writing, [Caldern, et al \(2017\)](#) concludes that the best grammar instruction is that which gives the greatest return for the least investment of time. Shaughnessy advocates three important concepts: the grammar, organization and mechanics. She recommends that teachers encourage students to examine grammatical errors in their own writing. She also cautions teachers not to overemphasize grammatical terminology to the detriment of students' ability to understand and apply the concepts.

[Hui, et al \(2021\)](#) proposes a vocabulary has to be studied as a social phenomenon. We don't make up language for no reason; rather, it serves as a means of conveying the ideas and concepts that unite us as a species. Therefore, it is impossible to separate its study from its social meaning, which is comprised of a number of factors that together determine its interpretation. Many experts in different domains have independently come to the same conclusion on this.

Findings of the Study

1. It is revealed that in terms of Grammar, General Academic Track gathered the highest median score of 18.57 with the verbal interpretation of Good, it is followed by the Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics strand with the mean score of 18.33 and a verbal interpretation of Good. Accountancy, Business and Management strand is on the 3rd spot with a mean score of 16.66 with the verbal interpretation of Good. Lastly, the Technical and Vocational Livelihood – Information and Communication Technology got a mean score of 12.35 with a verbal interpretation of Fair. Data showed that majority of the strand in Mary and Jesus School Inc. is Good in Grammar.
2. The result yielded to Fair in terms of Organization in the English Writing Proficiency of the Grade 11 Senior High school Students of House of Achievers Learning Center. General Academic Strand has the highest mean score of 4.93 with the verbal interpretation of Good. On the other hand, Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics strand got 4.30 mean score with a verbal interpretation of Fair, it was followed by Accountancy, Business and Management strand with a mean score of 3.64 with a verbal interpretation of Fair and lastly the Technical and Vocational Livelihood – Information and Communication Technology strand with the 2.38 mean score and Fair verbal interpretation.

3. The result showed that Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics strand got the highest median score of 22.44 with the verbal interpretation of Very good. It is followed by General Academic Track with the median score of 20.10 and with a Very Good verbal interpretation also. On the other hand, the Accountancy, Business and Management strand and Technical and Vocational Livelihood – Information and Communication Technology strand got a verbal interpretation of Fair with a median score of 12.20 and 12.08 respectively. Overall, in terms of Mechanics, the Grade 11 Senior High School students of House of Achievers Learning Center got a median score of 17.84 with a verbal interpretation of Good.
4. Using the Analysis of Variance Technique (ANOVA), the null hypothesis is rejected. It means that the English Writing Proficiency of the Selected Grade 11 Senior High School Students is significant when they are grouped according to strand. Therefore, the approaches and techniques used in teaching writing to Grade 11 Senior High School students must be different because their strength and weaknesses in writing are different.

CONCLUSIONS

In the light of the above findings, the following conclusions can now be made.

1. The results of this study emphasized that all of the four strands of Grade 11 Senior High school Students were "Good" in terms of Grammar. Most of them were "Fair" in terms of Organization. And in terms of Mechanics, majority of them were "Good".
2. The English Writing Proficiency of the Grade 11 Senior High School Students of House of Achievers Learning Center has significant difference when they are grouped according to strand. Thus, the hypothesis was rejected.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. House of Achievers Learning Center should give an enhancement program: workshop that focuses on grammar, organization, and mechanics.
2. The teacher should focus on the grammar skills in teaching and there must be additional reinforcement like drills that would enhance their grammar skills. On the part of the students, they must read more grammar books to gain knowledge.

The students must also focus in paragraph organization. They must spend more time in reading books that will help to gain more knowledge in Organizations.

In terms of Mechanics, all of the National High Schools should maintain the "Very Good". On the part of the students, they must familiarize the rules that will help them to be proficient in writing.

3. Lastly, this research could be used by the future researchers as a basis for further study related to the English writing proficiency.

APPENDIX

APPENDIX A - QUESTIONNAIRE

THE ENGLISH WRITING PROFICIENCY AMONG THE SENIOR HIGH STUDENTS OF HOUSE OF YOUNG ACHIEVERS LEARNING CENTER: BASIS FOR TEACHING STRATEGY IMPROVEMENT

Name (Optional): _____

Gender: _____

Strand: _____

I. Grammar

DIRECTIONS: Encircle the letter of the correct answer.

1. The lens of the camera _____ badly scratched.
a. is b. are c. were
2. Several people _____ coughing.
a. was b. were c. are
3. Mary _____ understand problem.
a. doesn't b. don't c. didn't
4. Special moments from a vacation _____ a great deal.
a. means b. meanc. meant
5. Those light bulbs on the dresser _____ frosted.
a. seems b. seem c. seemed
6. Each year in your life _____ by quickly.
a. fly b. flies c. flew
7. You _____ late for lunch.
a. was b. were c. is
8. Some of the hospitals _____ visiting hours for children.
a. has b. have c. had
9. The house with four bedrooms _____ sold quickly.
a. was b. were c. are
10. The rug on the wall _____ soft.
a. feels b. feel c. felt
11. A committee on solar heat _____ with energy problems.
a. deals b. deal c. dealt
12. The energy from coal _____ us warm this winter.
a. keeps b. keep c. kept
13. Our policy in these matter _____ a fair one.
a. is b. are c. were
14. The remarks _____ given by the President.

- a. was b. were c. is
15. He_____ want to hurt anyone’s feelings.
a. doesn’t b. don’t c. didn’t
16. The teacher has _____the dancers for the tinikling.
a. choose b. chose c. chosen
17. We _____ to FortSantiago last month.
a. go b. went c. gone
18. I have_____ too much suman.
a. eat b. ate c. eaten
19. Ana _____us two complimentary tickets to the movie.
a. give b. gave c. given
20. He _____to his relative in the United States.
a. write b. wrote c. written
21. The balagtasan _____an hour ago.
a. begin b. began c. begun
22. The bell has just _____for class.
a. ring b. rang c. rung
23. The tree has _____across the road.
a. fall b. fell c. fallen.
24. The thirsty puppy _____great amounts of water.
a. drink b. drank c. drunken
25. Who_____my dictionary?
a. take b. took c. taken
26. The teacher _____gently to erring student.
a. speak b. spoke c. spoken
27. The wind has _____all day.
a. blown b. blew c. spoken
28. What have you _____ with my ballpen?
a. do b. did c. done
29. I _____ my assignment in one hour.
a. do b. did c. done
30. Wehave_____our work well.
a. do b. did c. done

Source: Communication Skills by Josefina P. Gabriel -Building English Skills: Teacher’s Edition by Carol K. Kartons

II. Organization

A. Main Idea

DIRECTIONS: Read each paragraph and encircle the main idea.

1. It is important to protect yourself from the dangers of lightning. If you are outside when a thunderstorm begins, look for a building or car. Do not hide under a tall tree. Stay out of pools and lakes.

What is the main idea?

- a. Ways in protecting yourself from the dangers of lightning.
 - b. Tips to protect yourself from lightning.
 - c. How to protect yourself from lightning.
2. Stamp collecting is a hobby that attracts people in every country of the world. You can discover strange animals or beautiful works of art on stamps. You can meet famous people. With stamps you can even travel to distant lands.

What is the main idea?

- a. Why stamp collecting attracts people.
 - b. Stamp collecting is a hobby that attracts people.
 - c. Beautiful arts on stamps.
3. The old bicycle needed repair. Its handlebar was loose. Its seat was frayed and worn. The blue paint on the frame was scratched and faded. Both tires needed air. I could see why Mom wanted to throw it out.

What is the main idea?

- a. Old bicycle is too risky to repair.
 - b. The old bicycle needed repair.
 - c. Repairing an old bicycle is costly.
4. Everyone in my family enjoys a day at an amusement park. My little sister likes the pony ride. My big brother always rides the roller coaster. My mother loves to drive the beat-up cars on the Dodgem. I like the Ferris wheel the best.

What is the main idea?

- a. Why each member of the family likes the amusement park.
 - b. Amusement Park is very enjoyable.
 - c. The day at the amusement park.
5. Corey was nervous about his first day at the new school. He did not know any of the other children. The maze of hallways and stairs confused him. He wished he was back at his old school.

What is the main idea?

- a. Corey was nervous about his first day at the new school.
- b. Corey's first day at the new school.
- c. Corey's nervousness on the first day of a new school.

Source: Skills Practice Book: Building English Skills by McDougal Littell & Company

B. Logical Organization

DIRECTIONS: Rearrange the sentences in the following paragraphs according to the most appropriate order.

Encircle the letter of the correct order.

1. (1) Fish and other marine products abound in Philippine waters because its 7, 103 islands are surrounded by the China Sea, the Pacific Ocean, and the Sulu Sea.
(2) It has extensive forests and agricultural lands.
(3) It is rich in minerals, including gold, silver, copper, nickel, and iron.
(4) The Philippines has rich natural resources.
(5) It is one of the world's largest producers of sugar, bananas, mangoes, and copra.
 - a. 4, 3, 2, 5, 1
 - b. 2, 5, 3, 4, 1
 - c. 3, 4, 1, 2, 5

2. (1) The exchange rate has provided them with a price which would make growing them highly profitable.
(2) Our country has a great need for different kinds of food and feed.
(3) A number of these are still imported.
(4) If the people can get themselves involve in export-related industries, we will be better off.
(5) Besides, the new exchange rate will encourage export industries.
(6) There have been reduced controls over prices, so that farmers will get the full benefit of their produce.
 - a. 4, 3, 6, 2, 1, 5
 - b. 2, 3, 1, 6, 5, 4
 - c. 1, 5, 2, 4, 3, 6

3. (1) The proper practice of breastfeeding corrects malnutrition in infants.
(2) These cases of malnutrition have been traced to improper milk formula preparation and the lack of safe drinking water, especially in the rural areas.
(3) Breastfeeding contributes to our dollar-saving efforts since mothers do not have to buy formula drink that is usually manufactured by multinationals
(4) A common practice among rural mothers is to over-dilute the milk formula for their babies to stretch their supply of milk, thereby depriving the infants of much needed nutrients.
 - a. 3,1,2,4
 - b. 1,3,2,4
 - c. 2,4,3,1

4. (1) Flowers left by total strangers are an uplifting sight.
(2) They convey a message that all is not lost, that there is a reason to celebrate or to be alive that hope abounds, that there are fellow human beings who care.
(3) While flowers are offered to the sick, to the dying or to the dead, they nevertheless signify vibrance, exuberance, upliftment, and ultimately, hope.
(4) In times of tragedy or accident, compassionate people quietly leave offerings of flowers to signify their shared grief and their well- wishes.
 - a. 4,3,1,2
 - b. 3,4,2,1

c. 4,1,3,2

5. (1) A friend embraces another friend to drive away the latter's loneliness and sadness.
(2) The mother caresses the newborn and gives the baby the feeling of love and security that will be the foundation of the self.
(3) A doctor makes the mother feel her baby to give her satisfaction after her birth labor.
(4) This tactile stimulation often sends the most powerful messages.
(5) Touch is our most intimate and powerful means of communication.
(6) A father taps the shoulder of his son to boost the latter's sagging morale after a defeat in a school contest.
(7) A son holds the hand of his dying father in a final goodbye.

a. 3,2,6,7,1,4,5

b. 5,3,2,6,1,7,4

c. 2,3,5,7,1

Source: Phoenix Learning Package Skill Builders for Efficient Reading 8 by Arceli M. Villamin., College Freshman English Winning Strategies for Study, Thinking, and Writing Skills by Lourdes A. Dagdag et al.

III. Mechanics

DIRECTIONS: To make the paragraph correct, Underline the correct punctuation, capitalization and spelling inside the parenthesis.

The Beauty Remains;

The Pain Passes

[**althoughAlthough**] [**Henrihenri**] Matisse was nearly 28 years younger than [**Augusteauguste**] Renoir, the two [**great grate**] artists were dear friends and frequent companions[, .] When [**Renoirrenoir**] was [**conpined confined**] to his home during the last decade of his life [. ,] Matisse visited him daily. Renoir[, .] almost [**paralized paralyzed**] by [**atrithis arthritis**], continued to paint in spite of his infirmities. [**oneOne**] day as [**matisse Matisse**] watched the elder painter working in his studio [, .] fighting [**tortorous torturous**] pain with each brush stroke [. ,] he blurted out [: ;] " Auguste, why do you continue to [**paint faint**] when you are in such agony [! ?]"

[**renoir Renoir**] answered simply [: ;] " The [**beaty beauty**] remains [: ;] the pain passes." [**Andand**] so, almost to his dying day Renoir put paint to canvas. [**oneOne**] of his most [**famous famuos**] paintings, [**the Bathers The Bathers**], was completed just two years before his passing [. ,] 14 years after he was [**stricken stricken**]

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